

Earth as Text: Ecological Yearnings in Kalidasa's *Meghadutam* and Abhay K's *Monsoon: A Poem of Love and Longing*

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Abstract: *The Meghadutam which inaugurated in Sanskrit literature the genre of the messenger-poem or the sandesa kavya, is regarded by most scholars as the most ambitious work in Kalidasa's literary oeuvre. Abhay K's Monsoon: A Poem of Love and Longing, a single poem constituting hundred and fifty quatrains, describes the journey of the south-west Monsoon from the island of Madagascar across the Indian Ocean and the Indian subcontinent to the Himalayas. Its literary inspiration, quite obvious to most readers, is derived from Kalidasa's Meghadutam. The present paper attempts to undertake a reading of both texts from the point of view of contemporary theories in Ecocriticism. It shall endeavour to examine the poems as deep ecological texts which rather than privileging man's place in the natural world, craft a bio-centric narrative of love within which man, along with the myriad elements of nature, is intricately, inseparably, and humbly woven. By closely mapping the emotions of love, longing and desire in interrelationship with the elements of nature, both texts invest ecological landscape with a life of its own and bring thereby, the human and non-human worlds in a close and symbiotic structural alliance.*

Keywords: ecocriticism, nature, deep ecology, landscape, love

Man's relationship with nature has been, for a long period in human history now, complex and turbulent. While on the one hand, the physical bounty of nature has been universally acknowledged to be integral to human survival on earth, on the other, nature has almost always been culturally constituted as man's 'Other'- an entity outside of man that must be subdued, defeated, dominated and priced for its infinite secrets so that the end of human control over the natural world might be attained. While almost all ancient and pre-modern societies in human civilization, had based their worldviews on the belief that human beings constituted a minor and non-special part of the wide and all-encompassing fabric of natural life, the very idea of modernity particularly in the West, seems to have established itself on the premise of man's exclusion from and superiority over other elements in the natural world, an idea responsible for forging the dangerous binary of Man/Nature which, as many ecological critics have pointed out, complicate our responsibility and ethical stance towards the eco-system that we inhabit. The questioning of man's place within the framework of the natural world has therefore been one of the fundamental areas of ecocritical enquiry since the emergence of the discipline in the 1960s, leading to the generation and development of multiple and often conflicting points of view on the subject. The various approaches taken by scholars and environmentalists on this issue may roughly be divided into two camps – the anthropocentric view of nature which accords greater significance to human beings and their values on the scale of existence and the bio-centric or earth-centric view of nature which formulates that humans share the universe with an infinite number of species to none of whom is allotted greater claim over its assets and resources.

The latter point of view is today better understood in Arne Naess's terms as 'deep ecology' and is an approach characterized, as Naess states, "by our deep relationship with the environment and a joyful acceptance of this relationship." (131) While the anthropocentric view of nature, also often termed as 'shallow ecology', insists on the active preservation and protection of the environment in the

interests of man, and the longevity of his race on earth, deep ecology reads the human species as merely one strand in the entire web of natural life and concentrates on the protection of nature not for the sake of humans but for its own immense and intrinsic value. For the deep ecologist, as Naess points out, “the whole planet, Gaia, (that) is the basic unit, and every living being has intrinsic value.” (135) In the words of Naess:

The deep ecology movement is a total view. It covers our basic assumptions, our life philosophy, and our decisions in everyday life. I have also called the total view an “ecosophy” in order to distinguish it from ecology as a science. *Sophia* is Greek for wisdom. So, ecosophy means eco-wisdom, and wisdom has always been related to practice. (134)

Deep ecology bases itself on the inviolable premise that the human self is basically ecological and intuitively attuned to the consciousness of nature so that the protection and nurturing of the natural environment are not goals extrinsic to human well-being but acts compulsive and integral to our lives on this planet. Deep ecologists in contrast to shallow ecologists believe that the world’s environment problems cannot be solved by science and technology alone but by going deep within our self and by cultivating and trusting our basic intuitions towards nature. As Bill Devall states:

As we discover our ecological self, we will joyfully defend and interact with that with which we identify; and instead of imposing environmental ethics on people, we will naturally respect, love, honor and protect that which is our self. (43)

Read in the light of the principles of deep ecology then, Kalidasa’s *Meghadutam* seems to manifest itself as a literary embodiment of Naess’s ecosophy, for the text through its expanse, description and intention, offers to the reader an experience which aims at extending the frontiers of realization beyond the immediate level

of the human ego to a large-scale embracing of the landscape and the environment as a whole. The *Meghadutam* which inaugurated in Sanskrit literature the genre of the messenger-poem or the *sandesa kavya*, is regarded by most scholars as the most ambitious work in Kalidasa's literary oeuvre. Rendering immortal the love-message sent through a cloud by a despairing *yaksha*, pining in punished separation from his distanced beloved, the poem stands unchallenged in world literature till date in its exquisite craftsmanship, its effusive lyricism and its profound explorations of the *vipralambha sringara*, the emotion of love-in-separation. The lush, luxuriant and erotic descriptions of the natural world that accompany the *yaksha*'s elaborate directions to the cloud concerning the geographical path to *Alaka*, his mythical home where his wife suffers in isolation their painful bereavement, have called forth the admiration and critical engagement of readers and scholars in almost every generation. My reading of the text, however, shall attempt to interpret its natural descriptions not as ornamental imagery that heighten the impact of the human subject of love explored by the poem but as the central subject of the poem itself. The chief intention of this paper shall lie in its establishment of the poem not merely as a message of human love as it is generally supposed to be, but as an erotic awakening of nature at the call of the monsoons into which the human narrative of love and longing too is seen to be indistinguishably woven. Having thus made a case for reading the poem as an earth-centric love narrative, the paper shall insist upon its status as a deep ecological text that attempts to humble rather than exalt man's place in nature by looking upon the entire natural world with its abundant elements and inhabitants inclusive of man, as a single, seamless and integrated whole.

Most critical commentaries on the *Meghadutam* in Sanskrit credit it with being the harbinger of a new poetic genre, that of the *sandesa kavya* or the 'messenger poem' whose plot involves two separated lovers and constitutes in the sending of a message by the one to the other. There are reputed to be around 250 *sandesa kavyas* in Sanskrit, all inspired by the *Meghadutam* and each,

following the structure of Kalidasa's poem, is divided into two parts – the first part describing the messenger and the route to be taken while the second enlightens the reader about the destination, the recipient and the message itself. Another significant characteristic of these poems following Kalidasa, is the use in all of them of a non-human messenger to convey the message of love. While it is certain that Kalidasa had precedents of the use of non-human messengers before him such as in the epical use of the monkey-god Hanumana to convey Lord Rama's message to Sita in the *Ramayana* or in the use of a goose to convey a message of love between Nala and Damayanti in the *Mahabharata*, the use of an inanimate element of Nature such as a cloud for the purposes of communication between lovers had never been conceived in literary imagination before. Kalidasa himself is aware of this literary innovation and in the fifth stanza, at the very beginning of the poem, he inserts a sort of narrative aside trying to pass off his protagonist's use of the cloud for communication as an instance of pathetic fallacy, an erroneous identification made by the yaksha in a love-lorn state:

What! A cloud? A tumble of vapour, heat, water,
wind
To deliver a message from sentient living beings
Not figuring that the eager yaksha
Asked it – him – cloud
The lovelorns' nature is such – poor things –
They cannot discriminate
between animate-inanimate (7)

However, if one reads the poem in the context of the historical culture that produced it, there is no element of pathetic fallacy here for Kalidasa's text was intended to speak to a culture that was still acutely aware of pantheistic ideas and in which elements of nature like the sun, clouds, certain plants, trees etc. were known to be in possession of special powers and capable of granting human wishes. Besides, if pathetic fallacy characterizes the yaksha's mistaking of the cloud as animate, then it can be said to

characterize a good deal of the entire poem which treats mountains, flowers, trees, rivers and birds with the same sensitivity as is accorded to the scant human figures who fleetingly register their visibility in the text. In fact, I would like to argue that the use in figurative terms of pathetic fallacy which prompts the yaksha to call upon the cloud to act as messenger, is central to the ecosophical approach of the poem, for the cloud, a product of the union between earth and sky, air-borne and capable of traversing whole landscapes in its task of bearing and shedding water, functions as, perhaps, the best symbol of ecological interrelatedness. The cloud as messenger communicates to the entire world of nature the message of the arrival of the monsoons and calls forth, as the poem documents, a response rich and nuanced in its diversity and beauty. It is no wonder then that the despondent yaksha too, separated from his beloved for one whole year by the irrevocable punitive order of his lord, Kubera, invokes the mighty cloud to carry to his wife a message of his well-being. The use of the cloud as a messenger for human emotions militates against a worldview that compartmentalizes the human and non-human worlds, seeking rather to bring them into ecological contiguity. There is no pathetic fallacy in this, for as Neil Evernden insists, "...once we engage in the extension of the boundary of the self into the "environment" then of course we imbue it with life and can quite properly regard it as animate – it is animate because we are a part of it." (101) The pathetic fallacy is thus, as Evernden insists, "a fallacy only to the ego-clencher." (101)

Abhay K's *Monsoon* traces the path of the monsoon which originates near Madagascar and traverses the Indian Ocean to reach the Himalayas and back to Madagascar. As monsoon travels across the Indian Ocean islands, the Western Ghats, East and North India, Bhutan, Nepal and Tibet, it traverses a rich geographical, cultural and linguistic territory in a way reminiscent of Kalidasa's *Meghdutam*. Here, the idea of a letter sent through the cloud-messenger is only a thinly veiled contrivance for professing a love of another kind, one that is both profoundly ecological and staunchly territorial. The ecological thrust of Abhay K's work is

not far to seek. *Monsoon* abounds in the fecundity and glory of all forms of plant and animal life – terrestrial, aquatic and aerial. There is, throughout the book, a rich sampling of the biota of the various geographical regions that the cloud traverses and lest these connections should be missed by readers, the poem is accompanied by elaborate footnotes that enhance our repertoire of geographical information in compound ways. Thus, Mantellas, we come to know, are golden or multicoloured poison frogs of the Madagascar and that the Sifaka, also known as the dancing lemur, is a critically endangered species of lemurs. The range of geographical references in *Monsoon* is stunning and encyclopaedic. Yet the urge that dominates the poem is not the catalogic or the documentary. What is, rather, at work here is a keen ecological activism that seeks to offer due space, value and representation to the intense drama of the non-human world that largely goes unseen and ignored.

Through the aerial and egalitarian vision of the monsoon, Abhay K notes the complex interpenetration of land, locality, nature, culture, community, biosphere and more. Accompanying his ecological concern in *Monsoon* is a focused territorial concern. Every landscape, with its ecological and human wealth, is a distinct cultural script that articulates a heritage. A locality is an identifiable coordinate not only on the geographical map but on the cultural map of the globe as well. Localities are created by idiosyncratic and multilayered umbilical relationships between geography, nature and culture. As such, every locality constitutes a unique geographical and cultural fingerprint. Abhay K realizes the threat to the local in a global world and attempts to resurrect in *Monsoon* the vibrant localities of, as he puts it in his Introduction, “the Indian Ocean islands of Madagascar, *Réunion*, *Mauritius*, *Seychelles*, *Mayotte*, *Comoros*, *Zanzibar*, *Socotra*, *Maldives*, *Sri Lanka*, *Andaman & Nicobar* and the Indian subcontinent into one poetic thread.” (i) Unlike the cloud-messenger in the homologous world of Kalidasa’s *Meghadutam*, the contemporary cloud-messenger traversing a passage from Madagascar to Srinagar must bear witness to the mini-narratives of postcolonial and postmodern

diversity that characterize this terrain and must speak for the rich localities that it encounters enroute. Hence, ecological descriptions in *Monsoon* fuse with sharp territorial signifiers of landmarks, monuments, cuisines, languages, fashion, rites and rituals. Thus, Kerala's *kettuvallam* cruises, Karnataka's Tulu language, the hot springs of Rajgir, Bihar's *laai*, *tilkut*, *anarsa*, Kumbhalgarh's Badal Mahal, Chandigarh's Sukhna Lake and old Delhi's Ghalib ki Haveli at Gali Ballimaran, to mention just a handful, come together in this poem to reinstate the anthropological value and charm of locality in public memory. Idyllic as this mode of memory-making is, it is not naive of the region's history of migration and loss. Thus, the whiffs of old Bhojpuri and Gujarati carried by the monsoon from the Indian Ocean islands will always remind the Indian speakers of these languages of a past that can, perhaps, be recovered only in the imagination.

Experiencing an essential nonduality of spirit awakens us to the realization that our human and non-human worlds are coterminous, mark each other dialogically, and are firmly embedded in one other. Both *Meghadutam* and *Monsoon*, if one technically analyzes them, are plot-less, consisting in the mere verbal instructions to a cloud to deliver a message of love, the actual physical delivery of the message being secondary to their purposes. Besides, the greater part of the poems is seen to be devoted to describing the cloud's journey rather than the message which should, in generic terms, constitute the central motivation of the poem. The poems are clearly more obsessed with the cultural fact of the cloud as messenger of nature and with the cloud's particular aerial point of view as it traverses extensive geographical territories than the human pain of separation. In describing the cloud's detailed journey to their homelands, both poems seem to be evoking nostalgia of another kind - that of the exile in whose subconscious, memories of home and family are closely intertwined with geographical memories of the native landscape. Besides being alive to the geographical, botanical and zoological wealth of the landscape, the poems are also acutely aware of the land's rich cultural history and fuse details from epics, myths and legends

which have been enacted on this sacred ground. Thus, Kalidasa directs the reader's attention to the waters where Sita bathed, to the sacred places marked by Lord Rama's footprints, to the towering shrine of Mahakala (Lord Shiva) at Ujjainito Devagiri - the seat of Skandha, to the sacred battleground of Kurukshetra, and to Shiva and Parvati's mythical home in Kailasa. The reader is reminded of the various narratives of the land – the descent of the river Ganga on earth; the story of Parasurama whose axe flung, cleft the mountain; the story of Bali whose pride was shattered by the Vamana avatar of Vishnu; the story of Ravana attempting to uproot the Himalayas in a bid to plant it his own garden and so on. Similarly, Abhay K. calls our attention to the rich bio-diversity of the Indian Ocean Islands and the Indian Subcontinent: “Radiated tortoises carrying galactic maps/ Soumanga sunbirds sipping nectar/ white Sifakas dancing in herd/ ring-tailed lemurs feasting on Baobab flowers/ Vasa parrots courting their mates” (3) The subject of deep ecological writing is this dialogue between man and nature.

In discussing about the place of humans in nature, eco-theorist Christopher Manes writes:

As hominids, we dwell at the outermost fringes of important ecological processes such as photosynthesis and the conversion of biomass into usable nutrients. No lofty language about being the paragon of animals or the torchbearer of evolution can change this ecological fact – which is reason enough to reiterate it as often as possible. (24)

He insists that it is the discourse of humanism since the ages of the Renaissance and the Enlightenment that has culturally legitimated Man's power over nature and its reduction in turn, to a passive subject. It is high time, in his opinion, that humans renounced this anthropocentric language in favour of another tongue “free from the directionalities of humanism, a language that incorporates a decentered, postmodern, post-humanist perspective”, a language,

in other words, of “ecological humility”. (17) It is my opinion that *Meghadutam* and *Monsoon*, in portraying the entire natural world as inspired, articulate, intelligible and communicative rather than as passive and inert, seek to offer for our understanding and appreciation just such a language of “ecological humility”. By inspiring and lending voice to entire landscapes with their teeming ecological fertility and by humbling man’s place in it in treating him as a definite though not distinctive strand in the web of natural life, both texts seem to be definitely espousing a deep ecological stance, vitally necessary for our times.

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